

**THE IMPACTS OF RAINFALL ON AIRCRAFT
MOVEMENTS
IN AKURE AIRPORT**

**AN ORIGINAL PROJECT BY
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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this final year project was compiled and written by LATEEF MAYOWA BENJAMEN of the department of Transport Management Technology, Federal University of Technology Akure Ondo State, in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of Bachelor of Technology (B. Tech) in Transport Management Technology.

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DEDICATION

To the Almighty God I **LATEEF MAYOWA BENJAMEN** dedicate this thesis to. Also to my parents Chief and Mrs. Gbadamosi Olu Lateef. I say a very big thank you I am forever grateful for your love and care, and your contribution in my life.

ABSTRACT

This research work evaluates the impacts of rainfall on flight movement in Akure Airport. This study focused on the monthly and annual occurrence of rainfall, trend/pattern of rainfall and its influence to the number of flight diversions, delays and cancellations. In order to evaluate this impact, two years data on rainfall frequency and the numbers of flight diversions, delay and cancellations were obtained. The statistical analysis employed were the simple and multiple bar charts. From the analysis, it was observed that rainfall occur mostly between June and October with more occurrence of moderate rainfall measured (when the precipitation rate is between 2.5mm(0.098in)-(0.30in) or 10mm(0.39in) per hour) also there are rare cases of flight diversions, delays and cancellations because they are few numbers of aircraft movements at the airport daily.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Flight movement at the airport is one of the major determinant of how effective the operations of the airport are being scaled upon which consist of the operational and administrative parastatals around the globe whose aim is centralized on safety. In view of this in other to enhance the flight operation at the airport proper plans are been set up in terms of security, documentations, structural and transportation within the airport among others. (Clues, 1952)

In other to achieve the airport operational climax aim which is safety proper attentions are been drawn towards the aeronautical navigation system amidst the operations of the airport which involves plantation of navigational instruments [Non Directional Beacon (NDB), Very High Omni directional Rader (VOR)] among others, Air Traffic control (ATC), Aeronautical telecommunication(AEROCOMMS), which they all uses the information filled by the pilot with the local aviation authority called the flight plans. (Ian, Leon, & Moses, 1990)

Flight plans are documents filed by a pilot or flight dispatcher with the local Civil Aviation Authority (e.g. the FAA in the United States) prior to departure which indicate the plane's planned route or flight path. Flight plan format is specified in (ICAO, ICAO Publication, 2010). They generally include basic information such as departure and arrival points, estimated time of enroute, alternate airports in case of bad weather, type of flight (whether instrument flight rules [IFR] or visual flight rules [VFR]), the pilot's information, number of people on board and information about the aircraft itself. In most countries, flight plans are required for flights under IFR, but may be optional for flying VFR unless crossing international borders. Flight plans are highly recommended, especially when flying over inhospitable areas, such as water, as they provide a way of alerting rescuers if the flight is overdue. In the United States and Canada, when an aircraft is crossing the Air Defense Identification Zone(ADIZ), either an IFR or a special type of VFR flight plan called a DVFR (Defense VFR) flight plan must be filed. For IFR flights, flight plans are used by air traffic control to initiate tracking and routing services. For VFR flights, their only purpose is to provide needed information should search and rescue operations

be required, or for use by air traffic control when flying in a "Special Flight Rules Area". (Clues, 1952)

Flight plans are most time filed in a written form which might be through typing or E-Platform depending on the facilities of the aerodrome. It contains the information's about a particular movement of flight at a particular period of time (Josve05a, Flight plan (disambiguation), 2019).

Flight plans according to ICAO annex 16 talks about the components of flight plans which includes the aircraft call sign, equipment's, departure and arrival time, among others.

In other to achieve better effectiveness of this operation at the airport weather and climate cannot be overlook because improper management of it might be hazardous to the airport operations. (Remi 1987) in analyzing factors of air crash in Port-Harcourt Airport in 1987 stated that the prevalent weather at the time of the crash was thunderstorm. This occurrence had some negative impacts on flight operations. Country of the size of United States or Australia experiences approximately 10,000 thunderstorms each year Remi (1987).

Clouds, tugs atmospheric pressure amidst others affect the operation of flight but it's of no doubt that rainfall is a major factor that is not negligible. Rain is liquid water in the form of droplets that have condensed from atmospheric water vapor and then become heavy enough to fall under gravity. Rain is a major component of the water cycle and is responsible for depositing most of the fresh water on the Earth. It provides suitable conditions for many types of ecosystems, as well as water for hydroelectric power plants and crop irrigation. (Kempler, 2007).

The major cause of rain production is moisture moving along three-dimensional zones of temperature and moisture contrasts known as weather fronts. If enough moisture and upward motion is present, precipitation falls from convective clouds (those with strong upward vertical motion) such as cumulonimbus (thunder clouds) which can organize into narrow rain bands. In mountainous areas, heavy precipitation is possible where upslope flow is maximized within windward sides of the terrain at elevation which forces moist air to condense and fall out as rainfall along the sides of mountains. On the leeward side of mountains, desert climates can exist due to the dry air caused by down slope flow which causes heating and drying of the air mass. The movement of the monsoon trough, or intertropical convergence zone, brings rainy seasons to savannah climes.

The urban heat island effect leads to increased rainfall, both in amounts and intensity, downwind of cities. Global warming is also causing changes in the precipitation pattern globally, including wetter conditions across eastern North America and drier conditions in the tropics. (Oyenike , Ibidun, & Adebayo, 2014) Antarctica is the driest continent. The globally averaged annual precipitation over land is 715 mm (28.1 in), but over the whole Earth it is much higher at 990 mm (39 in). Climate classification systems such as the Köppen classification system use average annual rainfall to help differentiate between differing climate regimes. Rainfall is measured using rain gauges. Rainfall amounts can be estimated by weather radar. Rain is also known or suspected on other planets, where it may be composed of methane, neon, sulfuric acid, or even iron rather than water.

When evaluating airport operations related with rainfall and other related impacts, it became apparent that the associated were always recognized by the aviators. Severe rainfall significantly influences the safety and operational efficiency of air traffic, particularly at the terminal areas.

The unavoidable consequences of reduced efficiency are delays, diversions and cancellations of flights. This occurrence had some negative impacts on flight operations. Severe rainfall can be as destructive inform of erosion or flood. A single severe rainfall unleashes its fury over an area of about 8km. Sometimes, especially along a weather front, floods and erosions come in company and line up for more than 150km.

The International Air Transport Association (IATA) stated that 71% of air accidents in Nigeria are due to poor weather conditions. (NOAA 2004) affirmed that weather affects flight operations in Nigeria. Even before these cases, there has been a decline on the efficiency of flight operation in the country which is traceable to weather phenomena and their antecedent hazards.

Therefore, a good knowledge of this subject matter becomes very important to Aircraft operators, pilots and flight crew members and other lovers of aviation industries as safety of lives and properties should be ensured and risks reduced to the barest minimum. As such, the purpose of this study is to determine the impacts of rainfall on flight operations in Akure local Airport.

1.2 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Since the operations of the airport may not survive without the pre information of the flight to be operated. In other to access the impacts of the flight plans been filed the upon aircraft movements these questions should be answered.

What are the characteristics of rainfall at Akure airport?

What are the cases of delays, cancellations, diversions of flights due to rainfall?

What are the mitigating strategies applied during cases of delays, cancellations and diversions?

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to assess the impacts of rainfall on flight movement in Akure airport in respect to Enhancing Capacity, Service, Safety, and Environmental Compatibility.

The specific Objectives are to:

1. To examine the temporal characteristic of rainfall at Akure Airport for 2017 and 2018.
2. To identify cases of delays, cancellations, diversions of flights due to rainfall for 2017 and 2018.
3. To assess the mitigating strategies applied during cases of delays, cancellations, diversions of flights due to rainfall.

1.4 STATEMENT OF REASERCH PROBLEM

Although air transportation seems to be the best way of travels in most part of the world sometimes it became unsafely and unreliable due to the different factors including bad weather such as heavy rains. Bad weather may lead to aircraft crashing, delaying, cancellation of flight, diversion of flights to other alternate aerodromes. If crashing occurs it expose passengers and crew in the high risk and damage to the aircraft, therefore the loss of income for the owner of that damaged aircraft as well as government though taxes.

In Nigeria many cases of flight accidents are reported which associated with weather, also many cases of delay, cancellation of flight are still reported much during long and short rain seasons.

Flight operations in Akure airport are now frequent unlike many years ago when the operation activities are not frequent. With this respect flight are been planned through the use of flight plan

but most of the time the flight plans are not been followed as appropriate as a result of some unexpected circumstances that rises especially during the departure and arrival of flight.

Therefore, one of the factors that affect Akure airport operation that will be considered for the purpose of this research is rainfall. How it affects the movement of flight and everything that concerns it.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will help in improving the safety and profitability of the air transportation companies, people who are using airways for their safaris and government. Also the study will help in reducing accidents, understanding local climatology and will provide information for future planning.

1.6 SCOPE OF STUDY

The study will concentrate mainly on the landing and take-off stages of an aircraft at Akure airport as these are the phases of flight for which data is available.

1.7 OPERATIONAL TERMS

Instrument Flight Rule – (IFR)

Visual Flight Rule – (VFR)

Very High Omni directional Radar – (VOR)

Non Directional Beacon – (NDB)

Instrument Landing System – (ILS)

Flying Through the Airspace Region – (ENROUTE)

Air Traffic Control – (ATC)

Aeronautical Information Service – (AIS)

International Civil Aviation Organization – (ICAO)

Intra Seasonal Oscillations – (ISO)

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter shows a broader knowledge on aircraft movements, rainfall and other extreme weather events, it also shows past research on impacts of extreme weather events on aviation as a whole. It also states relevant and empirical framework (Kempler, 2007).

In this chapter, we will help reveal the gap that exists in the body of the literature that this study tends to fill. During landing of aircraft the microwave landing system is very important in order to avoid an accident/ crashing, The Microwave Landing System (MLS) is in the process of being implemented worldwide as the new all-weather landing system for aircraft. It will replace the existing Instrument Landing System (ILS) (Ian, Leon, & Moses, 1990) One of the operational requirements for the system is to guide aircraft to runway touchdown in all weather conditions (termed Category III). Testing conducted in recent years has demonstrated the sensitivity of the performance of the microwave antennas to the presence of water on the antenna aerodrome.

The effects can include not only degradation of the radiated signal but also degradation of system monitoring. Research has been conducted to find a radome material with hydrophobic (water shedding) properties sufficient to prevent the accumulation of water on the radomes and thereby eliminate its effects. The radome material also needs to have a sufficient lifetime that it does not create maintenance problem. Testing conducted in recent years has demonstrate that, during rainfall the sensitivity of the performance of the microwave antennas are very poor due to present of water on antenna radome, because water on antenna radome of aircraft causes loss of accuracy, effective radiated power and system monitoring. (Cassell,1990).

Rainfall presents major problems on flight plans in different areas around the world, rain is the most weather cases reported in many countries in which causes interruptions of flights especially when it is associated with poor visibility In such poor visibility operation must be stopped by ICAO recommendations, therefore no aircraft allowed to land or take off until improvement achieved (ICAO, 2012).

Airline flight schedules and delays for one specific route from Los Angeles to San Francisco during the month of September, He found that airlines do tend to pad their scheduled to give the appearance that flights arrive on time more frequently (Burgauer 2000).

2.1 FLIGHT PLANING

Flight planning is the process in whereby the pilot filed the flight plan as a document prior to its departure with the local aviation authority (Josve05a, Flight planing, 2019). The components of flight plans are stated and explained below.

2.1.1 AIRCRAFT IDENTIFICATION

Aircraft registration letters/tail number or an ICAO agency designator with flight number. ICAO 2012 strictly enforces that this figure should be letters and numbers only, devoid of dashes, spaces, or other punctuation. i.e. NGR001, GCABC, KLM672, SWIFT45 and so on.

2.1.2 FLIGHT RULES

Denotes the category of flight rules: “I” for IFR, “V” for VFR, “Y” for when the flight will be initially IFR followed by one or more subsequent flight rules changes, and “Z” for VFR first with any number of subsequent changes. When a “Y” or “Z” flight is prepared, “VFR” or “IFR” must be entered in the route string wherever the transitions/changes to the flight rules are planned to occur. i.e. Departing VFR, cruising IFR, and landing VFR? File Z.

2.1.3 TYPES OF FLIGHT

Denotes the type of flight as follows: “S” for Scheduled Air Service, “N” for Non-scheduled Air Transport Operation, “G” for General Aviation, “M” for Military, and “X” for everything else. Other special flight status and handling considerations can be relayed via the 18 OTHER INFORMATION field’s “STS/” and “RMK/” indicators.

2.1.4 NUMBER

Number of aircraft in flight, if more than one. This figure is omitted if the flight is only a solo aircraft movement.

2.1.5 TYPE OF AIRCRAFT

Type of aircraft, as specified in the latest ICAO Doc 8643, by the appropriate designator. A search for this designator code can be performed online at:

(ICAO, ICAO Publication, 2010) If no designator exists for your aircraft, or there is more than one type of aircraft in your flight, enter “ZZZZ” here and specify number and type(s) in 18 other information preceded by “TYP/” tags. i.e. P46T, EA50, C182.

2.1.6 WAKE TURBULENCE CAT

Wake turbulence category of aircraft as specified in ICAO Doc 8643 or based on weight and the following options: “L” for Light (< 7,000 kg), “M” for Medium (7,000 to 136,000 kg), “H” for Heavy (> 136,000 kg), and “J” for Jumbo (exceptionally heavy aircraft such as the Airbus A380-800). A search for the category can be performed online at: (ICAO, ICAO Publication, 2010)

2.1.7 EQUIPMENT

The ICAO 2012 amendment includes extensive changes to the COM/NAV equipment codes used in the FPL message format. These changes and EuroFPL’s helpful ICAO 2012 Equipment Wizard are explained in-depth on the next page (Page 3) of this briefing. (ICAO, 2012)

2.1.8 DEPARTURE AERODROME

Four-character location indicator of the departure aerodrome, “AFIL” if filed in the air, or “ZZZZ” if no official designator exists in ICAO Doc 7910. In the latter cases, ICAO 2012 strictly states that the aerodrome name or primary fix with location (degrees and minutes ddmmNdddmmE format preferred) be entered in 18 OTHER INFORMATION preceded by a “DEP/” tag. i.e. EKRK, BIKF, LFPG, CYYR, ZZZZ and so on.

2.1.9 TIME

Planned time of departure (UTC) in 24-hour “HHMM” format, where “HH” is a two-digit representation of the hour, and “MM” is a two-digit representation of the minutes past the hour (with leading zeroes where necessary) i.e. 0615, 1342, 2305 (ICAO, 2011).

2.1.10 CRUISING SPEED

True airspeed for the initial or whole cruise segment of the flight, indicated as: “N” for Knots, followed by a four-digit figure, “M” for Mach number followed by a three-digit representation of ratio, or “K” for Kilometers/hour followed by a four-digit number i.e. K0830, N0485, M082 (ICAO, 2011)

2.1.11 LEVEL

Planned cruising level for the initial or whole cruise segment of the flight, indicated as: “F” for Flight Level in 100s of feet, “A” for plain altitude in 100s of feet (both three-digit), “S” for Standard Metric Level in tens of metres, “M” for plain altitude in tens of metres (both four-digit), or “V” for uncontrolled VFR (number field left blank). i.e. F330, M0840, A045... (ICAO, ICAO Publication, 2010)

2.2 WEATHER FORECASTING

A forecast is a concise statement of expected meteorological conditions at an aerodrome or over an area or along a route. Owing to the variability of meteorological elements in space and time, the limitation of forecasting techniques, and the limitations imposed by the definitions of some of the individual meteorological elements (e.g. surface wind, weather), the specific value of any forecast element is to be understood as being the most probable value which the element is likely to assume during the period of the forecast. Similarly, when the time of occurrence or change of an element is given in a forecast, this is to be understood to be the most probable time. (ICAO, 2011)

Meteorological service for international aviation is provided by meteorological authorities designated by States. Details of the meteorological service to be provided for international (ICAO, 2011)aviation are determined by each State in accordance with the provisions of Annex 3and with due regard for regional air navigation (RAN) agreements, which apply to specific areas designated as air navigation regions by ICAO. Each State also establishes a suitable number of meteorological offices, i.e. aerodrome meteorological offices, meteorological watch offices (MWOs) and aeronautical meteorological stations. Meteorological offices and aeronautical meteorological stations provide information required for operational planning, flight operations, the protection of aeronautical equipment on the ground, and for various other

aeronautical uses (Ian, Leon, & Moses, 1990). The information provided includes observations and reports of actual weather conditions at aerodromes and forecasts; it is made available at aerodrome meteorological offices and is disseminated as appropriate to aeronautical users, including operators, flight crew members, air traffic services (ATS) units, search and rescue (SAR) units, airport management and others concerned with the conduct or development of international air navigation (USAirforce, 2005).

Forecasts of en-route conditions, except forecasts for low-level flights issued by meteorological offices, are prepared by world area forecast centers (WAFCs). This ensures the provision of high-quality and uniform forecasts for flight planning and flight operations. It also permits MWOs to concentrate on keeping watch on weather conditions in their flight information regions (FIRs) and permits meteorological offices at aerodromes to concentrate on local aerodrome forecasting, to keep watch over local (aerodrome) conditions and to issue warnings of weather conditions that could adversely affect operations and facilities at the aerodrome (e.g. aerodrome and wind shear warnings) (ICAO, 2011).

SIGMET and AIRMET information concerning the occurrence of specified en-route phenomena which may affect the safety of aircraft operations are issued by MWOs. In the specific case of tropical cyclones and volcanic ash, in addition to SIGMET, advisory information is issued by designated tropical cyclone advisory centers. The responsibility for the provision of meteorological service for international air navigation mentioned in rests with the meteorological authority designated by each State in accordance with (ICAO 2011) Annex 3, 2.1.4. The meteorological (MET) authority may wish to provide the service or may arrange for the provision of the service by other providers on its behalf. Terms additional to the “MET authority” are being used in the context of safety oversight audits related to institutional arrangements in States. In particular, use of the terms “meteorological (MET) inspectorate”, “meteorological (MET) regulator” and “meteorological (MET) service provider” has raised questions. The “MET inspectorate” refers to the entity that is responsible for conducting safety oversight for the “MET authority” over the “MET service provider” in the State concerned; The “MET regulator” can be considered to be simply another term for the “MET authority”, i.e. the body responsible for the facilities and services to be provided in accordance with (ICAO 2011) Annex 3. This term is used to highlight the regulatory aspects of its functions; and the “MET

service provider” is the entity that is providing the MET facilities and services as required in ICAO provisions. In the context of safety oversight audits, the term “entity providing the MET service” is sometimes used to designate the “MET service provider”. (ICAO, 2011)

There are no provisions currently in place that would prevent the “MET inspectorate” to be part of the same organization as the “MET authority”. Furthermore, in accordance with (ICAO 2011) Annex 3, the “MET service provider” could be either within the “MET authority” or, alternatively, within an independent organization. However, in some States or regions (e.g. under the European Single Sky), the legislation stipulates that the “MET regulator” (i.e. “MET authority”) and the “MET service provider” have to be separated, at least functionally. In cases where the “MET service provider” is part of the same organization as the “MET authority”, it would be preferable that the oversight function be carried out by an outside, independent “MET inspectorate”. In such cases, the inspectorate could be an independent MET expert involved in the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) certification audit of the “MET service provider”, or be part of the ministry overseeing the “MET authority” or part of the civil aviation authority (CAA), provided that such a CAA-based inspectorate is a third-party, independent body with qualified MET personnel. Such arrangements would avoid any conflict of interest between inspection and service provision. Irrespective of the administrative arrangements, it is considered important that the “MET inspectorate” have close coordination with the entity responsible for the more general safety oversight (located in most cases within the CAA).

In order to meet the objectives of meteorological service for international air navigation and provide users with the assurance that the service, including the meteorological information provided, complies with the aeronautical requirements, the MET authority must establish and implement a properly organized quality system in accordance with the ISO 9000 series of quality assurance standards. The system is to be certified by an approved organization (Ian, Leon, & Moses, 1990).

Properly educated and trained personnel should be employed in the provision of meteorological service for international air navigation. It is, therefore, an important responsibility of the MET authority to ensure that widely recognized standards are applied to the qualifications, education and training of all of the personnel involved in the provision of meteorological service for

international air navigation. With respect to meteorological personnel, the requirements of the WMO should be applied.

2.3 METEOROLOGICAL WATCH OFFICES (MWOS)

States accepting responsibility for an FIR have to either designate an MWO to serve that FIR or arrange for another State to designate a MWO on its behalf. The MWOs designated in accordance with RAN agreement are listed in the relevant ANP/FASID to indicate the overall plan for providing meteorological service for the FIR within each ICAO region. They maintain a continuous watch over meteorological conditions affecting flight operations within their areas of responsibility, issue information on the occurrence or expected occurrence of specified hazardous en-route weather conditions which may affect the safety of aircraft and low-level aircraft operations (SIGMET and AIRMET information, respectively) and supply this and other weather information to their associated ATS units, usually an area control centre (ACC) or a flight information center (FIC). In addition, MWOs exchange SIGMET information issued by other MWOs as required by RAN agreement. The AIRMET information issued is transmitted to MWOs and meteorological offices in adjacent FIRs (for details see Chapter 4). In preparing SIGMET and AIRMET information, MWOs normally make use of special air-reports, and satellite and radar data. MWOs also supply the information received on pre-eruption volcanic activity, volcanic eruptions and volcanic ash clouds, for which SIGMET information has not already been issued, to their associated ACC(s)/FIC(s), and in accordance with RAN agreement, to the VAACs concerned. It is also the responsibility of MWOs to supply information received concerning an accidental release of radioactive materials into the atmosphere within the area of their responsibility to their associated ACC(s)/FIC(s) and to the relevant AIS units, as agreed by the ATS, AIS and MET authorities concerned. This information is usually obtained from the WMO regional specialized meteorological centre (RSMC) which specializes in the provision of computer-generated dispersion model products for radiological environmental emergency response.

2.4 TROPICAL CYCLONE ADVISORY CENTER (TCACs)

TCACs are meteorological centers designated by RAN agreement on advice from WMO. They monitor the development of tropical cyclones in their areas of responsibility, using geostationary and polar-orbiting satellite data and other meteorological information sources (e.g. numerical

weather prediction models). TCACs provide MWOs, providers of international OPMET databanks established by RAN agreement, providers of the aeronautical fixed service (AFS) satellite distribution systems and, as necessary, other TCACs with advisory information regarding the position of the centre of the tropical cyclone, its forecast direction and speed of movement, central pressure and maximum surface wind near the centre of the cyclone. The advisory information is to be used by MWOs in support of the issuance of SIGMET information for tropical cyclones. The information is also made available to aeronautical users through the AFS satellite distribution systems.

2.5 VOLCANIC ASH ADVISORY CENTER (VAACs)

VAACs are meteorological centers designated by RAN agreement on advice from WMO (ICAO, ICAO Asia Pacific Air Navigation Planning and Implementation Regional Group, 2012). They monitor relevant satellite data to detect volcanic ash in the atmosphere. Subsequently, VAACs run volcanic ash numerical dispersion models to forecast the movement of a volcanic ash cloud. VAACs maintain contact with State volcano agencies in their respective areas of responsibility in order to obtain expert and timely information on significant pre-eruption volcanic activity and volcanic eruptions of concern to international air navigation. As a result, the VAACs provide, as required, MWOs, ACCs, FICs, NOTAM offices, WAFCs, international OPMET databanks established by RAN agreement, AFS satellite distribution systems and other VAACs, with advisory information regarding the lateral and vertical extent and forecast movement of volcanic ash in the atmosphere following volcanic eruptions. The advisory information is to be used by MWOs in support of the issuance of SIGMET information on volcanic ash clouds. The information is also made available to aeronautical users through the AFS satellite distribution systems.

VAACs form part of the ICAO International airways volcano watch (IAVW). The international arrangements set up within the IAVW are aimed at monitoring volcanic ash in the atmosphere and providing warnings to aircraft of volcanic ash and associated volcanic activity.

2.6 LOCAL SPECIAL REPORTS

Local special reports are issued in addition to local routine reports to provide information on significant deteriorations or improvements in aerodrome meteorological conditions at the aerodrome concerned (ICAO, ICAO Publication, 2010). They are issued whenever one or more

elements of a routine report change in accordance with criteria established by the meteorological authority in consultation with the ATS authority, the operators and others concerned. These criteria include: those values which correspond to the operating minima of the operators using the aerodrome; those values which satisfy other local requirements of ATS units and of the operators; an increase in air temperature of 2°C or more from that given in the latest report, or an alternative threshold value as agreed upon between the meteorological authority, the appropriate ATS authority and the operators concerned; the available supplementary information concerning the occurrence of significant meteorological conditions in the approach and climb-out areas. Local special reports in respect of RVR, surface wind or other elements need not be issued if the local ATS unit(s) has displays for these elements corresponding to the displays in the meteorological station, or if changes in RVR are continuously reported to the ATS unit by an observer at the aerodrome. Displays of automated aerodrome meteorological observing stations located at the local ATS units are widely used to meet this requirement.

2.7 TERMINAL AERODROME FORECAST

Terminal Aerodrome Forecast (TAF) follow the general form of METAR. They include surface wind, visibility, weather phenomena and cloud, and relevant significant changes thereto. (ICAO, 2011) Forecasts of weather phenomena are for the area at the aerodrome, i.e. the area within a radius of approximately 8 km of the aerodrome reference point. The word “approximately” is used to cater for aerodromes that have perimeters which are not precisely a radius of 8 km from the aerodrome reference point. Forecasts of cloud are for the aerodrome and its vicinity (ICAO, ICAO Asia Pacific Air Navigation Planning and Implementation Regional Group, 2012), i.e. the area within a radius of approximately 16 km of the aerodrome reference point. Forecasts of maximum and minimum temperatures are included subject to RAN agreement. Detailed technical specifications for TAF are in Annex 3, Appendix 5, Table A5-1, (ICAO, 2011) which also includes an extensive set of examples relating to individual portions of the forecast. TAF valid for less than 12 hours are issued every 3 hours and those valid for 12 hours or more are issued at 6-hour intervals. The validity period of TAF is determined for each region on the basis of RAN agreement but must be between 6 and 30 hours inclusive. When issuing TAF, meteorological offices ensure that only one TAF is valid at an aerodrome at any given time.

TAF should be kept under continuous review to enable the issuance of amendments as necessary. Annex 3 does not explicitly require that complete METAR be available to maintain such a review (although many States do stipulate in their national regulations that METAR be required for this purpose). It is recommended that other sources of meteorological information be used in the absence of full METAR, e.g. weather radar data, observations from automatic weather stations, satellite images, etc. TAF that cannot be kept under continuous review must be cancelled.

2.8 TREND FORECASTS

In most ICAO regions, landing forecasts are supplied. They are prepared in the form of trend forecasts which consist of a concise statement indicating any significant changes expected to occur during the next two hours in one or more of the following meteorological elements: surface wind, visibility, weather and cloud. The trend forecast is always appended to a local routine or special report, or METAR or SPECI. Forecasts of weather phenomena are for the area at the aerodrome, i.e. the area within a radius of approximately 8 km of the aerodrome reference point. The word “approximately” is used to cater for aerodromes that have perimeters which are not precisely a radius of 8 km from the aerodrome reference point. Forecasts of cloud are for the aerodrome and its vicinity, i.e. the area within a radius of approximately 16 km of the aerodrome reference point. Detailed technical specifications concerning trend forecasts can be found in Annex 3, Appendix 3, Tables A3-1 and A3-2 (ICAO, 2010). (ICAO, 2011)

2.10 MODELLING THE CLIMATE SYSTEM

In general terms, a climate model could be defined as a mathematical representation of the climate system based on physical, biological and chemical principles (Johnson, 2018). The equations derived from these laws are so complex that they must be solved numerically. As a consequence, climate models provide a solution which is discrete in space and time, meaning that the results obtained represent averages over regions, whose size depends on model resolution, and for specific times. For instance, some models provide only globally or zonally averaged values while others have a numerical grid whose spatial resolution could be less than 100 km. The time step could be between minutes and several years, depending on the process studied. (Johnson, 2018)

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of the development and use of a climate model.

2.11 A REVIEW OF SIMILAR EXTREME WETHER EVENTS ON AIRCRAFT MOVEMENTS.

2.11.1 Icing

Several years of earlier research was conducted for the U.S. Air Force, related to the impact that warhead-induced damage had on the aero elastic integrity of lifting surfaces and in turn the resulting upset of the complete aircraft. This prompted us to look at how similar aeroelastic events and aircraft upsets might be triggered by ice accumulation on specific parts of the aircraft. Although seldom studied, icing can also significantly impact the aircraft's aeroelastic stability, and hence the overall aircraft stability and control, and can finally result in irreversible upset events. Ice accumulation on aircraft, and the resulting aerodynamic unsteadiness and possible stability upsets of the entire aircraft, are undesired. Research on these upsets is of high importance, since ice protection systems are not able to completely eliminate the presence of ice accumulation on aircraft. Structural ice formation on leading edges of wings and control surfaces initiate significant regions of unsteady flow. (Ronald and Tinney (2010).

In the period of 1990 - 2000, a total of 3,230 aircraft accidents were recorded by the Air Safety Foundation. Twelve percent of those were related to icing. In one type of aircraft, most of the icing accidents occurred during the approach and landing phases when the aircraft was flying at a higher angle of attack when compared to cruise flight. Studies on ice-related accidents of small general aviation aircraft have revealed that in many cases even the most experienced pilots have less than 5 to 8 minutes to escape the harmful icing conditions before their aircraft experiences violent upsets. (Johnson, 2018).as a result of this effects icing has a great impact on flight operations.

2.11.2 Thunderstorm

One of the greatest dangers associated with flight movement is thunderstorms. When evaluating accidents related with thunderstorms and other related impacts, it became apparent that the dangers associated were not always recognized by the aviators. Severe thunderstorm significantly influences the safety and operational efficiency of air traffic, particularly at the terminal areas. The unavoidable consequences of reduced efficiency are delays, diversions and cancellations of flights (Remi 1987). In analyzing factors of air crash in Port-Harcourt Airport in 1987 stated that the prevalent weather at the time of the crash was thunderstorm(Remi 1987) (Australian Government Bureau of Meteorology, 2006). This occurrence had some negative impacts on flight operations. Country of the size of United States or Australia experiences approximately 10,000 thunderstorms each year (Remi, 1987). Severe thunderstorm can be as destructive as a tropical cyclone or a tornado. A single severe thunderstorm unleashes its fury over an area of about 8km. Sometimes, especially along a weather front, thunderstorms come in company and line up for more than 150km. Annually, their destructive power results in economic losses of about \$2 billion. In Australia, thunderstorms are more damaging than cyclones, floods or bushfires.

It is a known fact that thunder occurred before lightning, it was caused by the collision of clouds, the sound was produced by resonance between high and low clouds, and by high clouds descending and colliding onto low clouds. And because of the built energy and intensity of thunderstorm, it becomes dangerous and unsafe for aircrafts wherever it is building.

2.11.3 Humidity

Humidity presents a problem if the moisture in the air condenses on the electronics used. Water can cause electronics to short, which results in erroneous behavior, loss of functionality, or high amounts of heat output that could lead to a fire. (Clues, 1952)

The basic of aircraft operation is electronic powered, besides those that are mission specific (e.g., camera), are to provide communication, command, and control. Some examples of these electronics include autopilots, flight controllers, receivers, servos, electronic speed controllers, and motors. The loss of functionality of any of these during flight is detrimental to mission success and likely to result in a crash.

A short that results in an electrical fire is particularly dangerous when operating with LiPo batteries. These batteries release hydrogen as part of their discharge. If a LiPo battery is damaged, the buildup in hydrogen combined with the sparks from a short can result in an explosion (Drone Registration 2016). For this reason, LiPo batteries are contained in plastic housing and sealed with Kapton tape or other insulating materials to prevent damage to the battery (Seidle, 2014). This being the case, small amounts of water on the battery itself will most likely cause no harm. The danger comes from the potential for other electronics to catch fire near the battery.

Maximum relative humidity specifications on aircraft range typically from 50% to 100%. Humidity is a greater problem in the morning, when there are relatively lower temperatures and higher humidity levels. According to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Association (NOAA 2016), the average relative humidity levels between the hours of 4 am and 6 am are greater than 50% for all 50 states in the US. Furthermore, relative humidity varies significantly with geographic location. In areas with high average humidity, it is particularly important to check humidity levels before flight and verify that electronics are watertight. (Josve05a, Flight plan (disambiguation), 2019)

2.11.4 Wind

Wind direction and speed can make a flight time quite different, for exactly the same journey. A tail wind – which pushes the aircraft forward through the air – will increase the aircraft's ground speed and shorten the journey. (Twidell, 2019)

A head wind – where the aircraft is flying against the wind direction – obviously does the opposite, slowing the aircraft’s ground speed and making the journey time longer.

Figure 2.2 Wind at 250 millibar (Jan 8 2015)

These time differences are most dramatically seen on transatlantic flights, due to jet streams. Jet streams are strong westerly winds that blow in a narrow band in the Earth’s upper atmosphere – at the altitudes used by most aircraft. Where these packets of fast moving air form a tube, they are called jet streams. Aircraft are built and tested to withstand strong winds, but strong winds can be a factor in a turbulent journey. While turbulence can be a worry, it isn’t a safety concern. For take-off and landing, aircraft always move into the wind to reduce the ground speed. Cross winds can also make take-off and landing more challenging. So airports will impose limits if the wind is moving across the runway. Many airports have runways facing in different directions to mitigate against cross winds, allowing the pilots to use the runway that faces into the wind (ICAO, 2012).

2.11.5 Clouds

A less-talked-about weather phenomenon to also think about are thunderstorms and clouds; Cumulonimbus clouds, commonly referred to by pilots as “CBs,” can be problematic as they are associated with heavy and sudden down pours of rain. These clouds are often caused by periods of very hot weather (Josve05a, Flight planing, 2019).

Private jets are usually better equipped to deal with CBs – they can climb faster and to get you above these clouds quicker than a commercial airliner, and can take more creative routes to avoid them in the air where commercial aircraft don’t have as much flexibility.

In addition, private jets are more agile and maneuverable, making landings in rough conditions much more flexible and safe.

Just be wary, often a private jet will delay takeoff if there are CBs directly overhead – it's entirely for your safety, but it may cause unforeseen delays.

2.11.6 Fog

All aircraft, including private jets, are affected by fog and poor visibility, which can sometimes cause flight delays. Although many commercial aircraft are equipped with auto-land autopilots (that can land the aircraft in zero visibility), it is on the ground and during take-off that most of the air traffic delays occur. (Twidell, 2019)

When the visibility at an airport drops below one mile (described by pilots and airports as RVR – Runway Visual Range) the airport enforces Low Visibility Procedures (LVPs). During LVPs, Air Traffic will reduce the number of aircraft taxiing and taking off to prevent accidents and incidents occurring.

Fog is often patchy and variable – with some airports affected while others remain clear. So just as with snow, a private jet flight allows for last minute changes during foggy weather, finding gaps in the fog and re-routing the flight accordingly – not an option open to airlines.

2.11.7 Sun

Aircraft can operate perfectly safely in sunny weather, and in hot temperatures (up to 127F, depending on the aircraft type). But a high air temperature does change the performance of the aircraft. (Twidell, 2019)

Hot air is thinner than cooler air. And this affects the output of the aircraft's engines as well as aerodynamic capabilities, increasing the required runway distance and reducing climb performance and the maximum payload. Pilots can opt to use a higher engine thrust setting when it's particularly hot.

So while it's rarely hot enough for flights to be grounded, it's something that needs to be factored into the flight plan.

Of course, however hot (or cold) it may be outside, the cabin temperature of a private jet is always set to the passengers' preference!

2.12 A REVIEW ON THE FORMATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF RAIN

Air contains water vapor, and the amount of water in a given mass of dry air, known as the mixing ratio, is measured in grams of water per kilogram of dry air (g/kg). The amount of moisture in air is also commonly reported as relative humidity; which is the percentage of the total water vapor air can hold at a particular air temperature. How much water vapor a parcel of air can contain before it becomes saturated (100% relative humidity) and forms into a cloud (a group of visible and tiny water and ice particles suspended above the Earth's surface) depends on its temperature. Warmer air can contain more water vapor than cooler air before becoming saturated. Therefore, one way to saturate a parcel of air is to cool it. The dew point is the temperature to which a parcel must be cooled in order to become saturated. There are four main mechanisms for cooling the air to its dew point: adiabatic cooling, conductive cooling, radiational cooling, and evaporative cooling. Adiabatic cooling occurs when air rises and expands. The air can rise due to convection, large-scale atmospheric motions, or a physical barrier such as a mountain (orographic lift). Conductive cooling occurs when the air comes into contact with a colder surface, usually by being blown from one surface to another, for example from a liquid water surface to colder land. Radiational cooling occurs due to the emission of infrared radiation, either by the air or by the surface underneath. Evaporative cooling occurs when moisture is added to the air through evaporation, which forces the air temperature to cool to its wet-bulb temperature, or until it reaches saturation.

2.12.1 Black Rain Clouds

As these larger water droplets descend, coalescence continues, so that drops become heavy enough to overcome air resistance and fall as rain. Coalescence generally happens most often in clouds above freezing, and is also known as the warm rain process. In clouds below freezing, when ice crystals gain enough mass they begin to fall. This generally requires more mass than coalescence when occurring between the crystal and neighboring water droplets. This process is temperature dependent, as super cooled water droplets only exist in a cloud that is below freezing. In addition, because of the great temperature difference between cloud and ground level, these ice crystals may melt as they fall and become rain. Raindrops have sizes ranging from 0.1 to 9 mm (0.0039 to 0.3543 in) mean diameter but develop a tendency to break up at larger sizes. Smaller drops are called cloud droplets, and their shape is spherical. As a raindrop

increases in size, its shape becomes more oblate, with its largest cross-section facing the oncoming airflow. Large rain drops become increasingly flattened on the bottom, like hamburger buns; very large ones are shaped like parachutes. Contrary to popular belief, their shape does not resemble a teardrop. The biggest raindrops on Earth were recorded over Brazil and the Marshall Islands in 2004 — some of them were as large as 10 mm (0.39 in). The large size is explained by condensation on large smoke particles or by collisions between drops in small regions with particularly high content of liquid water.

2.12.2 Acidity

The phrase acid rain was first used by Scottish chemist Robert August Smith in 1852. The pH of rain varies, especially due to its origin. On America's East Coast, rain that is derived from the Atlantic Ocean typically has a pH of 5.0–5.6; rain that comes across the continent from the west has a pH of 3.8–4.8; and local thunderstorms can have a pH as low as 2.0. Rain becomes acidic primarily due to the presence of two strong acids, sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) and nitric acid (HNO_3). Sulfuric acid is derived from natural sources such as volcanoes, and wetlands (sulfate reducing bacteria); and anthropogenic sources such as the combustion of fossil fuels, and mining where H_2S is present. Nitric acid is produced by natural sources such as lightning, soil bacteria, and natural fires; while also produced anthropogenically by the combustion of fossil fuels and from power plants. In the past 20 years the concentrations of nitric and sulfuric acid has decreased in presence of rainwater, which may be due to the significant increase in ammonium (most likely as ammonia from livestock production), which acts as a buffer in acid rain and raises the pH.

Rainfall intensity is classified according to the rate of precipitation, which depends on the considered time. The following categories are used to classify rainfall intensity:

- Light rain — when the precipitation rate is < 2.5 mm (0.098 in) per hour
- Moderate rain — when the precipitation rate is between 2.5 mm (0.098 in) - 7.6 mm (0.30 in) or 10 mm (0.39 in) per hour
- Heavy rain — when the precipitation rate is > 7.6 mm (0.30 in) per hour or between 10 mm (0.39 in) and 50 mm (2.0 in) per hour
- Violent rain — when the precipitation rate is > 50 mm (2.0 in) per hour

2.12 EMPIRICAL WORK

Table 2.1: Table showing the empirical work

S/N	Title of Article	Name of Author	Methodology	Findings	Gap
1.	Aerodynamic analysis under influence of Heavy rain	Tung Wan, Shi-Wei Wu	Secondary data	The aircraft engine has a direct relationship with the atmospheric condition. Especially turbine propelled engine	This method is fully efficient for analyzing the impact of weather on flight plan.
2.	Weather Impact on Airport Performance	Michael Schultz, Lorenz, Reinhard Schmitz and Luis Delgado	Secondary data	The weather has a major role on the landing of aircraft as it can results like aviation incidents and accidents.	The method is not efficient it only analyze airport facility.
3.	Exploring the range of weather impacts on UAS operations	Emily A. Ranquist Matthias Steinerand Brian Argro	Secondary data	Aircraft accident don't just happen but it is based on the range of the climatic	It is very efficient because the proper use of intelligent transport

				condition which can be regulated with proper monitoring..	system was made use which includes an high level of climatology
4.	Implication of Automatic Weather Observing Stations in Nigerian Meteorological Agency	Aderinto SA	Secondary data	Weather can be observed for a long period of time using WOS	It's not efficient because we have instance of extreme weather events
5.	Flying in the face of climate change: a review of climate change, past, present and future.	Watkinson AR, Gill JA, Hulme M	secondary data	Climate of the present, future and past has a relationship	Its is confirmed based on a region
6.	Tropical Climatology: An Introduction to the Climates of the Low Latitudes	Nieuwolt S.	secondary data	Rainfall is more frequent at the tropical area than others	Its confirmed based on history
7.	Aspects of Urban Climate	Omogbai BE	Primary data	Climate has no effect on	Its only true for business

	of Benin City			urbanization	trip only
8.	A note on the effect of urbanization on temperature in Ibadan	Adebayo YR	secondary data	Temperature has no effect on urbanization	Temperature has no effect on urbanization in Ibadan because
9.	Implication of Automatic Weather Observing Stations in Nigerian Meteorological Agency	Aderinto SA	Secondary data	Meteorological Agencies does not depends on WOS	Its not effective
10.	Temperature and relative humidity distributions in a medium-size administrative town in southwest Nigeria	Akinbode OM, Eludoyin AO, Fashae OA	Secondary data	Temperature and relative humidity as indirect effect on administration in southwest town in Nigeria	Its effective

2.13 CHAPTER SUMMARY

This chapter contained a literature review on impacts of extreme weather events on aviation transport. Specifically, this chapter reviewed flight plan and its relationship with aviation transport. Also this chapter underlines the importance of flight plan to improve aviation safety, to relieve traffic accident, to improve aviation transportation efficiency, to promote the

development of related industries and regulation of extreme weather events on aviation transport, including heightened terrorism/theft/security; information-sharing; regional multimodal logistical growth.

CHAPTER THREE

3.1 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design may be viewed from many perspectives and is often seen as controversial (Knox, 2004.). Because Research methodology comprises a body of knowledge that enables researchers to explain and analyze the research methods they use, indicating their limitations and resources, identifying their presuppositions and consequences, and relating their potentialities to research advances (Miller, 1983).

The choice of research method constitutes the foundation on which the entire research is conducted. In this chapter, the research methodology used in this study is described. In this chapter, the research methodology used in this study is described. The primary objective of this study is to know the impact of rainfall on flight plans by carrying out an evaluation on frequent occurrence of rainfall in relation to flight plans.

As it is indicated in the title, this chapter includes the research methodology of this research work. In more details, this part outlines the research strategy, the research method, the research approach, the methods of data collection, the selection of the sample, the research process, and the type of data analysis.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design refers to the general plan that a researcher follows when attempting to answer the research question(s) so that the different components of the study can be integrated into a coherent and logical structure (Saunders, 2003)

The research questions stated above will be answered by using Datas' from NAMA and NIMET.

3.3 STUDY AREA

Akure Airport is located at Kilometer 12 along Akure Owo Express Way it has 1 Runway, with 2800 meters long and 45meters width. The geographic coordinates of this airport are 7 degrees, 14 minutes, 48 seconds north (7.246739) and 5 degrees, 18 minutes, 4 seconds east (5.301008). Akure Airport is 1100 feet (335 m) above sea level using 30 degree Nautical miles. It facilitates her operation with a Visual approach with a locator beacon at frequency 276 kHz

3.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the temporal characteristic of rainfall at Akure Airport for 2017 and 2018.
2. To identify cases of delays, cancellations, diversions of flights due to rainfall for 2017 and 2018.
3. To assess the mitigating strategies applied during cases of delays, cancellations, diversions of flights due to rainfall.

3.5 RESEARCH POPULATION

Research population refers to the totality of elements, subjects or members that possess a specified set of one or more common characteristics that meets the researcher's interest (Donald et al, 2006).

The research population for this study will be based on the data from the airport operating agencies.

3.6 SAMPLE FRAME

The target for this study will be to use the report gotten from the NAMA, NIMET, travelers and the operators of aircraft at Akure airport

3.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

This study made use of the purposive sampling method with the use of secondary data, which was collected from different agencies. Weather data was collected and flight plan data was also collected at the Akure airport.

This study will adopt purposive sampling method to select its respondents. Participants for this study are the aircraft operators and individuals traveling through Akure Airport. Purposive sampling, is a non-probability sampling that satisfied certain criteria (Donald & Schinder, 2011) This is appropriate for this study due to time limitation for respondents to fill out the questionnaires. In total, 117 questionnaires were administered to the passengers from which 117 was collected making the response rate to be 100%, 100 passengers and 17 from the aircraft operators.

3.8 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Existing data's based on flight plans would be collected from the agencies involved. The data source would be secondary.

3.9 DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

Once the primary data is collected, it will be checked for completeness in readiness for the analysis. The responses from the field will be put into categories and coded according to the themes so as to answer the research question and obtain the relevant information. The classified data will now be presented in figures, tables and charts according to the study objectives for ease of interpretation, understanding, reading and discussion.

The secondary data collected from NAMA would be analyzed through proper grouping and correlated with the data of NIMET which would be subject to analysis then when times where there's is delay or cancellation has a result of rainfall would be noted.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion on the data gathered from the Nigerian Airspace Management Agency, Nigerian Metrological Agency and Questionnaires administered to the operational and passengers at the Akure Airport.

4.1 EXAMINING THE TEMPORAL CHARACTERISTIC OF RAINFALL AT AKURE AIRPORT FOR 2017 AND 2018.

FOR 2017

Table 4.1: Table showing the days and percentage of Rainfall intensity classified according to the rate of precipitation in 2017

	Days	%
Total days in a year	365	
Total days without rainfall	258	71
Total days with rainfall	107	29
Trace	15	4
Light rain	29	8
Moderate rain	37	10
Heavy rainfall	26	7
No Rainfall	258	71
Cases of cancellation	0	0

Figure 4.1 Pie chart showing the percentage of rainfall in 2017

Figure 4.2 Pie chart showing the percentage of Rainfall intensity classified according to the rate of precipitation in 2017.

For 2018

Table 4.2: Table showing the days and percentage of Rainfall intensity classified according to the rate of precipitation.

	Days	%
Total days in a year	365	100
Total days without rainfall	294	81
Total days with rainfall	71	19
Trace	8	2
Light rain	29	8
Moderate rain	22	6
Heavy rainfall	12	3
No rainfall	294	81

Figure 4.3 Pie chart showing the percentage of rainfall in 2018

Figure 4.4 Pie chart showing the percentage of Rainfall intensity classified according to the rate of precipitation for 2018.

Table 4.3: Table showing the 3-month average trend value of rainfall amount for 2017 and 2018

Month	Average Rainfall	3 monthly average Trend Value
January	0	
February	54.4	40.83333
March	68.1	66.73333
April	77.7	100.8
May	156.6	128.3
June	150.6	152.6667
July	150.8	187.0667
August	259.8	199.0667
September	186.6	175.5
October	80.1	88.9
November	0	26.7
December	0	0
January	0	0
February	0	11.13333
March	33.4	56.26667
April	135.4	85.9
May	88.9	143.0667
June	204.9	175.0333
July	231.3	169.1
August	71.1	139.6333
September	116.5	86.23333
October	71.1	101.3667
November	116.5	72.13333
December	28.8	48.43333

Figure 4.5: Figure showing the 3-month average trend value of rainfall amount for 2017 and 2018

From the table 4.1.1 and the figure 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 it can be said that the numbers of days without rainfall in akure airport are more compare to days there is rainfall. the 79% of days without rainfall was not evenly shared due to the fact that rainfall with moderate takes more of the percentage then followed by the light rain for 2017 while for 2018 from table 4.2.1 and figure 4.2.1 and 4.2.2 there are more days without rainfall compared with 2017. 89% of the days in the year are without rainfall and there are more of light rain followed by moderate rainfall.

Also considering the 3months trend analysis for the both year it is realized that the rainfall characteristics doesn't repeat itself but every month in a year has its own characteristics.

4.2 TO IDENTIFY CASES OF DELAYS, CANCELLATIONS, DIVERSIONS OF FLIGHTS DUE TO RAINFALL FOR 2017 AND 2018

Table 4.4: Table Showing the Cases of Aircraft Movements in 2017

	Numbers	%
Total number of aircraft movement	1522	100
Aircraft movement without any case	1509	99.1
Sum of cases	13	0.9
Cases not associated with rainfall	0	0
Cases associated with rainfall	13	0.9
Cases of delay	10	0.6
Cases of diversion	3	0.3
Cases of cancellation	0	0

Figure 4.6 Pie chart showing the cases of aircraft movement affected by aircraft in 2017

Figure 4.7: Pie chart showing the cases of delay, diversion and cancellation due to rainfall 2017.

Table 4.5: Table Showing the Cases of Aircraft Movements in 2018

	Numbers	%
Total number of aircraft movement	1021	100
Aircraft movement without any case	1013	99.3
Cases associated with rainfall	8	0.7
Cases not associated with rainfall	0	0
Sum of cases	8	0.7
Cases of delay	6	0.5
Cases of diversion	2	0.2

Figure 4.8: Pie chart showing the cases of aircraft movement affected by aircraft in 2018

Figure 4.9: Pie chart showing the cases of delay, diversion and cancellation due to rainfall in 2018.

Table 4.21 and 4.22 shows the cases of delay and diversion associated with rainfall. There are no cases of cancellation; this can be traced to the facts that there is minimal amount of flight operations in Akure airport. More also figure 4.1 shows that more cases of rainfall are light and medium rainfall. So the impact seems as minimal as most of them are not accompanied with extreme weather event.

Where we have more aircraft movement and frequent occurrence of extreme weather events there are more cases of diversion cancellation and diversion associated with rainfall.

4.3 TO ASSESS THE MITIGATING STRATEGIES APPLIED DURING CASES OF DELAYS, CANCELLATIONS, AND DIVERSIONS OF FLIGHTS DUE TO RAINFALL

Table 4.6: Table showing mitigating strategies that can be applied during the cases of delay, diversion and cancellation due to rainfall

		Passangers		Operators(%)
Rainfall has impact on		80		100

aircraft movement?				
Nothing can be done to mitigate the impacts of on aircraft movement?		40		88
Will still travel when there is dark cloud?		60		58.8
Consult taf/meter 3days before departure/arrival day		40		82
Other mitigating strategies		20		41

Figure 4.10: A bar chart showing the responses of the passenger’s and the aeronautical operators on the mitigating strategy applied during the cases of aircraft movement on rainfall.

Figure 4.31 shows the mitigating strategies applied by the operators and passengers in order to mitigate the impact of rainfall on aircraft movement. 80% of the passenger's believed that rainfall has a reasonable effect on aircrafts movement while 100% of the operators believed the rainfall has impact on aircraft movement in Akure airport. 40% of the passengers believed that nothing can be done to mitigate it while 88% of the operators believed it can be mitigated 60% of the passengers will still travel and 58.8% of operators decided that they will still proceed on the journey even when there is a sign of dark cloud.

Since the questioner for the mitigating strategies was open ended most people's expression on the mitigating strategies is to know the weather condition few days before that day so as to do proper aircraft movement planning in order to avoid all sort of cases unexpected. In other word few passengers of 20% and 41% of the operators chooses other mitigating strategies.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 FINDINGS

The objectives of this research were to identify the impacts of rainfall on aircraft movement. Based on the findings of this research it was gotten that as a result of small numbers of aircraft movements, the cases where there is rainfall and aircraft movement at the same time are rare situations. Locations where there is more aircraft movement and rainfall then there are more cases.

The best mitigating strategy based on the survey conducted on the aircraft operators and passengers is to get the TAF/METER weather forecast in order to prepare and schedule the aircraft movement and to avoid the cases of delay, diversion and cancellation of aircraft movement due to rainfall.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The best cases is what is on ground with little cases of delay, diversion and cancellation of aircraft due to rainfall though it's as a result of low amount of aircraft operation at the Akure Airport.

If there is more aircraft operation then there would be more cases of delay, diversion and cancellation of aircraft due to rainfall but if the operation continue like this then the cases will continue like this till when there are more aircraft operations.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The government and airlines should make more use of the airport to get other benefits like recognition rather than having little number of aircraft movement and the aviation workers should not cease to consult TAF/METAR as recommended by International Civil Organizations (ICAO).

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